

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

In the context of globalization and the accelerated development of digital technologies, industrial enterprises must adapt existing management systems to the modern requirements of the digital economy. This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of improving industrial enterprise management methodology in the context of digital transformation. Modern digital technologies influencing production processes, organizational structure, and management decisions are examined. Particular attention is paid to the implementation of artificial intelligence systems, big data, the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), ERP systems, and digital platforms. Directions for improving the efficiency of industrial enterprise management through digitalization are proposed.

Keywords: digital transformation, industrial enterprise, management, digital technologies, ERP system, innovation, industry, automation, digital economy.

1. Introduction.

The current stage of global economic development is characterized by the intensive implementation of digital technologies in all areas of economic activity. Industrial enterprises are becoming key participants in digital transformation, as industry forms the foundation for economic growth, innovative development, and increased national competitiveness.

In the context of digitalization, approaches to managing production systems are changing significantly. Traditional management methods no longer provide the necessary flexibility, speed of decision-making, and resource efficiency. This necessitates improving industrial enterprise management methodology using modern digital tools and technologies.

Digital transformation involves not only the automation of individual processes but also a comprehensive change in business models, organizational structure, decision-making systems, and corporate culture. In this context, the development of modern approaches to industrial enterprise management is particularly relevant.

2. Theoretical aspects of digital transformation of industry.

Digital transformation is the process of integrating digital technologies into all areas of an enterprise's activities, leading to qualitative changes in management systems, production, and interactions with consumers.

Figure #1. The main components of the digital transformation of industry¹

The digital economy is creating new demands on industrial enterprises. A modern enterprise must be highly adaptable, flexible, and able to respond quickly to changes in the external environment.

One of the key areas of digital transformation is the "Industry 4.0" concept, which involves the creation of intelligent production systems based on automation, robotics, and real-time data exchange.

Digitalization is having a significant impact on all elements of industrial enterprise management. First and foremost, it is changing management decision-making processes. Traditional management methods were based primarily on retrospective information and long-term data analysis. Modern digital technologies make it possible to obtain information in real time, predict changes, and promptly adjust management decisions.

¹Prepared by the author.

Major changes in the management system²

Process	Results
Automation of management processes	Automation reduces human error, improves operational accuracy, and lowers costs. Implementing ERP systems ensures the integration of a company's financial, production, and logistics processes.
Using Big Data	Big Data technologies make it possible to analyze vast amounts of information and identify patterns that impact production and management efficiency.
Application of artificial intelligence	Artificial intelligence helps automate analytical processes, forecast demand, optimize production cycles, and improve resource management efficiency.
Development of digital platforms	Digital platforms facilitate interaction between producers, suppliers, and consumers, creating a unified information environment.

Despite the significant benefits of digitalization, industrial enterprises face a number of challenges:

- insufficient level of digital infrastructure;
- shortage of qualified personnel;
- high costs of implementing digital technologies;
- resistance to organizational change;
- information security risks;
- insufficient integration of information systems.

One of the most serious problems is the lack of preparedness among management personnel to work in a digital economy. Effective digital transformation requires developing new competencies and a digital mindset.

To improve the efficiency of industrial enterprise management in the context of digital transformation, it is advisable to implement the following areas of improvement of management methodology.

Figure #2. Factors contributing to increased efficiency in industrial enterprise management in the context of digital transformation³

²Author's development.

³Prepared by the author during the research.

Companies that actively implement digital technologies demonstrate higher growth rates and resilience to external economic changes.

3. Foreign experience of the research.

In global scientific and practical literature, improving industrial enterprise management methodology in the context of digital transformation is considered within the context of the concepts of "Industry 4.0," "Smart Factory," digital ecosystems, and intelligent manufacturing. Particular attention is paid to the integration of digital technologies into production processes, the improvement of strategic management systems, the development of personnel digital competencies, and the formation of flexible organizational structures.

Research by the World Economic Forum, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, and McKinsey & Company has made significant contributions to the development of digital industrial transformation theory. Their studies note that digital industrial transformation involves not only the implementation of technologies but also changes to the entire enterprise management system, including organizational structure, decision-making methods, incentive systems, and corporate culture.

According to the "Industry 4.0" concept, digital transformation involves the widespread use of artificial intelligence, the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), big data, cloud computing, digital twins, and automated production management systems. Research shows that the implementation of these technologies can improve labor productivity, reduce production costs, reduce equipment downtime, and enhance production flexibility.

The "smart factory" approach, actively implemented in Germany, the United States, Japan, South Korea, and China, holds a special place in global practice. The German "Industrie 4.0" model views the industrial enterprise as a unified digital system, where all production processes are integrated through cyber-physical systems and intelligent control networks. The American approach emphasizes the use of platform solutions, big data analytics, and digital ecosystems to ensure enterprises are highly adaptable to market changes.

Research by the Global Lighthouse Network shows that digital transformation leaders achieve significant results through a comprehensive approach to production management based on the synchronization of business processes, technologies, and human capital. Specifically, the network's companies demonstrate increased labor productivity, reduced production costs, and increased supply chain resilience.

International researchers place particular emphasis on the human factor in digital transformation. Contemporary research emphasizes the need to shift from a purely technological approach to a human-centered model of industrial enterprise management. Within this framework, developing digital competencies among employees, providing intelligent operator support, and using augmented reality technologies in production process management are crucial.

International studies also show that successful digital transformation requires the development of a new management methodology based on:

- integration of digital technologies into strategic management;
- using real-time data;
- flexible management of production processes;
- development of platform business models;
- improving corporate governance;
- implementation of digital monitoring and forecasting systems.

At the same time, researchers note that one of the main problems of digital transformation remains the so-called "pilot trap" a situation in which enterprises successfully implement individual digital projects but are unable to scale them across the entire production system.

Global experience shows that improving industrial enterprise management methodology in the context of digital transformation should be based on the comprehensive integration of digital technologies, strategic management, innovative organizational approaches, and human capital development. This enables enterprises to ensure sustainable competitiveness, improve production efficiency, and adapt to the global digital economy.

4. Analysis and results of the study.

The research demonstrated that digital transformation has a complex impact on the management systems of industrial enterprises and is becoming a key factor in enhancing their competitiveness in the modern economy. An analysis of scientific literature, international experience, and current industrial development trends allowed us to identify key areas for improving management methodology in the context of digitalization.

The study found that the implementation of digital technologies significantly improves the efficiency of production and management processes. The use of ERP systems, Big Data technologies, artificial intelligence, the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), and digital platforms enables the integration of all enterprise business processes into a single information system. This significantly increases the speed of information processing, improves the quality of management decisions, and ensures operational control over production processes.

The analysis showed that digitalization contributes to:

- reduction of production costs;
- increasing labor productivity;
- reducing the time required to make management decisions;
- increasing the accuracy of planning;
- improving product quality;
- increasing the resilience of enterprises to external economic changes.

The research revealed that the most effective areas for improving industrial enterprise management are:

- automation of management processes;
- implementation of intelligent data analysis systems;
- development of digital infrastructure;

- integration of information systems;
- use of predictive analytics;
- development of digital competencies of personnel.

Research of global experience has shown that successful digital transformation requires a comprehensive approach, encompassing technological, organizational, and personnel changes. It has been established that companies implementing digital transformation systematically achieve higher economic results compared to those implementing individual digital solutions piecemeal.

At the same time, the analysis revealed a number of challenges hindering the effective digital transformation of industrial enterprises. Key issues include insufficient digital infrastructure, a shortage of qualified personnel, high costs of implementing digital technologies, information security risks, and resistance to organizational change.

The research's results confirm that improving industrial enterprise management methodology should be based on the principles of flexibility, adaptability, integration of digital technologies, and strategic management. Of particular importance are the use of real-time data, the development of intelligent decision-support systems, and the development of a digital corporate culture.

5. Conclusion.

In today's environment, digital transformation is becoming an imperative for industrial enterprise development. Traditional management methods are gradually losing their effectiveness, necessitating the development of new approaches to organizing production and management processes.

The research found that the implementation of digital technologies enables industrial enterprises to significantly improve operational efficiency, ensure resilience to external changes, and strengthen their competitive position in the market. ERP systems, artificial intelligence, Big Data, the Industrial Internet of Things, and digital platforms play a key role in improving management systems.

It has been established that successful digital transformation is impossible without a comprehensive improvement of management methodology, including:

- modernization of the organizational structure;
- development of digital competencies of personnel;
- integration of information systems;
- automation of business processes;
- improving strategic management.

Global experience shows that companies that actively implement digital technologies and modern management methods achieve higher productivity, innovation, and sustainable development.

Improving industrial enterprise management methodology in the context of digital transformation is a critical factor in increasing industrial efficiency and ensuring sustainable economic development. Prospects for further research include developing practical mechanisms for implementing digital technologies, refining

strategic management models, and assessing the effectiveness of industrial enterprises' digital transformation.

References

1. Abdullaev Sh.A. Modern approaches to the management of industrial enterprises in the context of digitalization // *Bulletin of Economic Research*. - 2023. - No. 2. - P. 28-35.
2. Ansoff I. *Strategic Management*. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2019.
3. Vikhansky O.S. *Strategic Management*. - Moscow: Gardariki, 2020.
4. Imomov N.N. Development of the digital economy and problems of industrial transformation in Uzbekistan // *Economy and Finance*. - 2021. No. 6. P. 14-21.
5. Castells M. *The Information Age: Economy, Society, and Culture*. Moscow: HSE, 2018.
6. Salimov B.T. Digital transformation of industry and improvement of management systems // *Economy and innovative technologies*. - 2022. No. 4. P. 45-53 Brynjolfsson E., McAfee A. *The Second Machine Age*. - New York: WW Norton & Company, 2014.
7. Brynjolfsson E., McAfee A. *The Second Machine Age: Work, Progress, and Prosperity in a Time of Brilliant Technologies*. - New York: W. W. Norton & Company, 2014.
8. *Capturing the True Value of Industry 4.0* // McKinsey & Company.
9. Davenport T. *Big Data at Work*. - Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014.
10. Davenport TH *Big Data at Work: Dispelling the Myths, Uncovering the Opportunities*. - Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014.
11. *Digital Transformation in Manufacturing: Global Lighthouse Network*. - Geneva: World Economic Forum, 2022.
12. Drucker P. *Management Challenges for the 21st Century*. - New York: Harper Business, 2007.
13. Gilchrist A. *Industry 4.0: The Industrial Internet of Things*. - New York: Apress, 2016.
14. Ivanov D., Dolgui A., Sokolov B. The Impact of Digital Technology and Industry 4.0 on the Ripple Effect and Supply Chain Risk Analytics // *International Journal of Production Research*. - 2019. Vol. 57. No. 3. P. 829-846.
15. Kagermann H., Wahlster W., Helbig J. *Recommendations for Implementing the Strategic Initiative INDUSTRIE 4.0*. - Frankfurt: Acatech, 2013.
16. Klaus Schwab. *The Fourth Industrial Revolution*. - Geneva: World Economic Forum, 2016.
17. Lee J., Bagheri B., Kao HA *A Cyber-Physical Systems Architecture for Industry 4.0-Based Manufacturing Systems* // *Manufacturing Letters*. - 2015. Vol. 3. - P. 18-23.
18. Matt C., Hess T., Benlian A. *Digital Transformation Strategies* // *Business & Information Systems Engineering*. - 2015. - Vol. 57. - No. 5. P. 339-343.

19. OECD Digital Economy Outlook 2020. - Paris: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2020.
20. OECD Digital Economy Outlook. - Paris: OECD Publishing, 2023.
21. Porter M., Heppelmann J. How Smart, Connected Products Are Transforming Competition // Harvard Business Review. - 2015.
22. Porter ME, Heppelmann JE How Smart, Connected Products Are Transforming Competition // Harvard Business Review. - 2014. Vol. 92. No. 11. P. 64-88.
23. Schwab K. The Fourth Industrial Revolution. - Geneva: World Economic Forum, 2016.
24. Schwab K., Davis N. Shaping the Future of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. - New York: Currency, 2018.
25. Tapscott D. The Digital Economy. - New York: McGraw-Hill, 2015.
26. Vial G. Understanding Digital Transformation: A Review and a Research Agenda // Journal of Strategic Information Systems. - 2019. Vol. 28. No. 2. P. 118-144.
27. Westerman G., Bonnet D., McAfee A. Leading Digital: Turning Technology into Business Transformation. - Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014.